

Testing Approaches for MSA-based Applications

Technique/Procedure/Others	Study ID	# of Studies
Integration testing	S02, S04, S08, S17, S21, S22, S23, S24, S28, S29, S30, S31	12
Unit testing	S02, S04, S17, S21, S22, S24, S29, S30, S31	9
Automated testing	S13, S17, S26, S20, S28	5
Black box testing	S02, S05, S03, S16 S25	5
Component testing	S04, S21, S22, S28, S30	5
Contract testing	S02, S21, S22, S30	4
Consumer driven contract testing	S11, S29, S31	3
System testing	S22, S23, S31	3
End to End testing	S24, S29	2
Load testing	S02, S27	2
Mocked data testing	S24, S28	2
Performance testing	S01, S30	2
Regression testing	S07, S31	2
Test driven development	S06, S17	2
White box testing	S03, S25	2
Scalability testing	S23	1
Formal method based testing	S15	1
Model based test generation	S16	1
Testing in production	S11	1
Acceptance testing	S05	1
Boundary value testing	S25	1
Change impact analysis testing	S25	1
Domain testing	S25	1
Evolutionary algorithms based testing	S09	1
Fault models	S10	1
Graph-based microservice testing	S14	1
Grey box testing	S16	1

GSAMRT	S31	1
Learning based testing	S20	1
Online system testing	S11	1
Risk based testing	S25	1
Run time testing	S12	1
Security testing	S30	1
Service and end user testing	S18	1
Service testing	S31	1
Session based workload models	S27	1
TTCN-3 testing language	S19	1